

Participatory Cultural Lexicography Innovating a dialectal dictionary by applying an Open innovation in science approach The example of exploreAT!

Eveline Wandl-Vogt, Amelie Dorn, Caitlin Gura

Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften
Wohlebengasse 12-14, 21040 Vienna, Austria

E-mail: [eveline.wandl-vogt](mailto:eveline.wandl-vogt@oeaw.ac.at) | [amelie.dorn](mailto:amelie.dorn@oeaw.ac.at) | [caitlin.gura](mailto:caitlin.gura@oeaw.ac.at) @oeaw.ac.at

3 Key words: Participatory Lexicography, Cultural Lexicography, Bavarian Dialects, Twentieth-Century Ethnography, Open Innovation in Science, Design Thinking

Abstract:

Across different scientific research areas there has been an increased emphasis on the development of participatory infrastructures to further communication and knowledge exchange across interdisciplinary networks. In this paper we address and introduce a scenario for participatory dialectal lexicography with an application of Open Innovation in Science methods in the larger context of Digital Humanities. The experiment is embedded in the project exploreAT! (Wandl-Vogt et al, 2015; Dorn et al, 2016), which deals with the content of the database of Bavarian dialects in Austria (DBÖ) from the aspects of cultural lexicography, visual analytics, semantic technologies and citizen science. In this paper we emphasise on the the citizen science aspect. We aim to engage the public in specific focus-groups in an experimental participatory approach for the development of relevant research questions during the whole research process and, ultimately, to collectively contribute and establish a common process structure for extracting cultural information from our data. In the approach we describe here, methods from Open Innovation and Design Thinking become inherent to this process.

While originally created within the realm of Business Management, the principles of Open Innovation and Design Thinking are expanding to a broad range of academic fields (Chesbrough 2003). By engaging a diverse team consisting of the public and researchers of various backgrounds and experiences, the research design process can become enriched and more inclusive through the team's active contributions in exploring and identifying the problem, ideation and conceptualizing a particular solution together (Stanford University Institute of Design 2017). Through a recurring series of workshops, the researchers and focus-groups discuss the abstract ideas and thoughts behind manifestations of culture. The results of these discussions are conceptualized within prototypes and subsequently tested and evaluated by both expert and novice users (i.e. the focus groups). However, the design process does not necessarily end at the end-product. Essentially, Design Thinking does not strictly focus on the results of the experiment, but rather the overall procedure (Razzouk and Shute 2012). Thus in this paper we exemplify the application of such methods in the field of lexicography in order to establish a participatory approach and collective effort linking different disciplines. We introduce how we apply above mentioned new methods in our experiments and we share first results, experiences and lessons learned from our cultural lexicography focus-groups (rural Austrian dialect-speakers, people with multicultural background in Vienna) with the community.

Bibliography

Chesbrough, H. (2003). *Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.

Datenbank der Bairischen Mundarten in Österreich/ *Database of Bavarian Dialects in Austria* (DBÖ). Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften. Wien.

Dorn, A., Wandl-Vogt, E., Bowers, J., Piringer, B. & Seltmann, M. (2016). exploreAT! – perspectives of exploring a dialect language resource in a framework of European digital infrastructures.1st International Congress on Sociolinguistics (ICS-1), Budapest, Hungary.

Razzouk, R. and Shute, V. (2012). What is Design Thinking and Why is it Important? in: *Review of Educational Research*. Washington, DC: American Educational Research Association, Vol. 82, No. 3 (September 2012), pp. 330-348

Stanford University Institute of Design. (2017). Our Point of View. Accessed at : <http://dschool.stanford.edu/our-point-of-view/#design-thinking>

Wandl-Vogt, E., Kieslinger, B., O'Connor, A. & Theron, R. (2015). „exploreAT! Perspektiven einer Transformation am Beispiel eines lexikographischen Jahrhundertprojekts“, in: *DHd-Tagung 2015*. Graz. Austria. Accessed at: <http://dhd2015.uni-graz.at> [12/04/2016]